

Barriers to Female Participation in Community-Based Organisations in the Kumbungu District of the Northern Region of Ghana

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Abstract – A Community-Based Organisation (CBO) is a voluntary autonomous association of people designed to meet their common economic, social, and cultural needs through a jointly owned and democratically managed organisation. Female participation in Community-based Organisations (CBOs) all over the world is one of the important factors which affect development in most communities. This term paper is about examining the barriers to female participation in CBOs in the Kumbungu District in the northern region of Ghana. The main objective of the study was to examine barriers to female participation in CBOs in the Kumbungu District of Ghana. A qualitative study design was used for the study and a purposive sampling technique was employed to arrive at 32 respondents. Data were collected through interviews with respondents to probe for detailed information on barriers to female participation in CBOs. The findings revealed a low level of participation of respondents, obstacles that serve as barriers challenging the active participation of respondents in their CBOs', and suggested advocacy and capacity building as mitigating factors to barriers of female participation in CBOs'. The study concludes that females face socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-political, and religious barriers in participation in youth associations that served as CBOs in the study area. The study suggested CBOs' activities on advocacy and capacity building to address the barriers to female participation in CBOs'. The study, therefore, recommends that CBOs' should organise sensitisation and training programmes for females on social and economic empowerment.

Keywords: gender, community-based, organisation, participation, barriers, development

1. INTRODUCTION

Although females in Ghana play a central role in community development through their contribution to household income and social equity, they are perceived as individuals relegated to the kitchen. The role of the northern woman in the contribution to labour and mentor cannot be measured, but their recognition has received nothing better than a nodding notification and only regarded as one of the few, and even then, their social contribution considered as just an *all-women affair* (Jackson, 2002). Also, their role in decision-making and leadership positions within community organisations remain negligible (Amir and Gati, 2006). In some cases, females are instructed to undertake tasks that are assigned by their *male masters* (Youth Opportunity Partnership Programme [YOPP], 2016). Moreover, the decision-making process has often relegated females to the background, except for decisions regarded as *all-female affaire* (Tanwir & Safdar, 2013). There is low participation of females in CBOs (YOPP, 2016). What accounts for this low participation of females in CBOs? Mutongu (2012) explains that females suffer from economic, social, cultural, political, and religious biases. These biases serve as barriers to their participation in CBOs. Can these barriers be found in the Kumbungu

District? It is in view of the above challenges that this paper examines the barriers to female participation in CBOs in the Kumbungu District.

The concept of Community-Based Organisation (CBOs) all over the world is one of the important approaches to community development over the years. A Community-Based Organisation (CBO) is a *voluntary autonomous association of people designed to meet their common economic, social, and cultural needs through a jointly owned, and democratically managed organisation* (Rabi & Mahendra, 2013:14). It is also an organisational entity made up of people whose membership is defined by a specific common bond and who voluntarily come together to work towards a common goal (Mulwa & Mala, 2000). The term participation has become a development orthodoxy holding out the promise of inclusion, of creating space for the less vocal and powerful to exercise their voices and begin to gain more choices in all aspects of development (Cornwall, 2003). Agarwal (2001) identifies levels of participation that represent an entire continuum. These are Nominal participation: membership in the group; Passive participation: being informed of decisions ex post facto; or attending meetings without speaking out; Consultative participation: being asked an opinion on specific matters without guarantee of influencing decisions; Activity-specific participation: being asked to (or volunteering to) undertake specific tasks; and Active participation: taking part in all aspect (formation, planning, decision making, leadership, and activities) of organisational development. There is a shift in the discourse on the level of participation beyond beneficiary participation to wider questions of citizenship, rights, and governance (Garventa, 2002). In some cases, the participation is activity-specific where females are instructed to undertake tasks that have been assigned by the men. In others, females participate only in the implementation and not in the decision-making process or the benefits generated (Tanwir & Safdar, 2013). This implies that merely taking part in the process is not sufficient and participation has to be an instrument that transforms and empowers females in the process. Combining the insights of Agarwal (2001) and Cornwall (2003), participation should be a transformative instrument that translates into social, political, economic, and cultural capital for both females and males, translating into more efficient and optimum rural development outcomes. It was predicted that females face barriers to actively participate in CBOs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The term participation has become development orthodoxy holding out the promise of inclusion, involving the less vocal and powerful to exercise their voices and begin to gain representativeness in all aspects of development (Cornwall, 2003). This idea of participation was highlighted by Agarwal (2001), which represents a diverse range such as Nominal participation: membership in the group; Passive participation: being informed of decisions ex post facto; or attending meetings without representing one voice; Consultative participation: being involved in opinion sharing on specific matters without the capacity to influencing decisions; Activity-specific participation: being authorised or volunteer to undertake specific tasks; and Active participation: Being a central element all aspects of decision making (formation, planning, decision making, leadership, and activities) of organisational development. Integrating the ideas of Agarwal (2001) and Cornwall (2003), participation is seen as a transformative instrument that translates into social, political, and cultural capital for both females and males, translating into more efficient and optimum rural development outcomes.

Concept of Community Based Organisation

The term Community-Based Organisation, or simply CBOs, may be associated with similar values but is generally more focused on issues particularly relevant to the community from which its membership is drawn. CBOs may be quite formally structured, but can equally be quite loosely structured informal organisations. CBOs, as components of larger civil society organisations, are ways of social capital that society consciously and voluntarily organises to achieve a common purpose (Boasu, 2011). The fundamental grounds for their formation are; ethnic, religious, social, economic, and gender basis, and represents a potent force for rural development. Their strength lies in their ability to mobilise people for communal labour and educational programmes (Opore, 2007). As a requirement for the formation, registration, and operations of self-help groups in Kenya, Winnie and Teresia established that CBOs ought to have common goals and concerns, be registered and recognised by the Ministry of Culture, Social Services & Sports, have guiding objectives for

their activities and be run by elected officials (Mutongu, 2012). Also, allowing full participation of all members, monitoring and evaluating its work, holding frequent meetings to enhance cohesion, being transparent and accountable for their actions, ensuring gender balance, engaging in group-building activity such as social events, and collaborating with other development agencies is a requirement for an effective CBO (Boasu, 2011).

Osei (2011) defines CBOs as a significantly self-help voluntary action group of people, who aim at satisfying the collective needs and aspirations of individual members. Collectively as members, CBOs share risks, enjoy together, and their leaders and managers are accountable for their stewardship. CBOs are generally assumed to form part of civil society, along with NGOs, social movements among others (Kamanzi, Nyankweli, Okwany, 2017). However, some have the role of deciding the use of resources that belong to the community as a whole (ACCORD, 2002). CBOs, according to Heather and Ann in Opare (2007), CBO's are formal or informal membership organisations serving particular interest groups usually in rural communities, whose focus may be broad or quite narrow.

Accordingly, Offei-Aboagye (1998) and Boasu (2011) also established that CBOs often demonstrate the capability to mobilise community resources for grassroots development and their members are usually resident in the communities and are well connected. Hence, they have the advantage of being keenly aware of local needs and are in a position to respond effectively and a lot more rapidly than either government agencies or NGOs. Thus, they are voluntary, not-for-profit, non-governmental organisations with aims and activities limited to a locality that has a unique identity (Boasu, 2011).

Theoretical Framework

The study is based on female participation which draws its significance on Gender and Development theories. In recent times, it is impossible to disregard the role of females in development. In this relation, there are many theories that emphasise the female's role in development. The major theories considered in this research are Women in Development (WID), Women and Development (WAD), and Gender and Development (GAD).

Women in Development (WID)

The term "women in development" came into light in the 1970s. It focused on mainstreaming women in development through equal access to education, property, and employment by skill training (Aryal, 2006). This approach was developed to recognise the role of women in development. The underlying rationale for the WID was that women are an untapped resource that can provide an economic and social contribution to development. The WID approach aimed at integrating women into the existing chain of development by targeting them often in women-specific activities (Bissabah, 2017). Essentially, WID gave primacy to women's productive roles and stressed the integration of women into the market economy, as it was based on the premise that women's subordination was directly linked to their exclusion from the system of development. One major drawback in WID, which has been criticised by so many writers like Moser (1993), Buvinic et al., in Bissabah (2017), is its focus on women in isolation. Women's issues were treated as an alienated and independent entity, completely separated from family, society, and community. The WID approach tended to focus exclusively on the productive aspects of women's work, ignoring or minimising the reproductive side of women's lives. Thus, WID typically has been income-generating where women are taught a particular skill or craft and sometimes are organised into marketing cooperatives. This is evident in the direct engagement of women in skills development in rural communities in the Northern region of Ghana (GDCA, 2015).

Women and Development (WAD)

The WAD came into existence in the second half of the 1970s. It draws its functional base from the dependency theory, for the most part, like Marxist analysis, has given remarkably little specific attention to issues of gender subordination. The Woman and Development approach provides a more critical view of women's position than WID (Bissabah, 2017). Women have always been part of the development process. The WAD perspective focuses on the relationship between women and development processes rather than purely on strategies for the integration of women into development. This approach accepts women as important economic actors in their societies (Burn, 2005). Theoretically, the WAD perspective recognises the

impact of class, but in practical project design and implementation terms, it tends like WID, to group women together without taking strong analytical notes of class, race, or ethnicity, all of which may exercise a powerful influence on women's actual social status. WAD offers a more critical view of women's position than does WID but it fails to undertake a full-scale analysis of the relationship between patriarchy, differing modes of production, and women's subordination, and oppression (Rathgeber, 1989). This was applicable in the formation of gender clubs within CBOs which serve the interest of females in their CBOs (YOPP, 2016).

Gender and Development (GAD)

In the 1980s, the approach of Gender and Development (GAD) had emerged as it focuses explicitly on improving women's status (Burn, 2005). The approach focuses on gender roles while criticising the gender about the structure (Rathgeber, 1989). The GAD approach takes into account the lives of women and labour, both inside and outside their homes. In addition, it emphasises a bottom-up approach, which argues that women are not as much integrated into development, as they are the architects of their development (Bissabah, 2017). Projects based on a GAD approach would be to encourage women to make positive change through women's organisations and activism. GAD emphasises on empowerment of women to work to change and transform the structures that have contributed to their subordination (Burn, 2005). This approach offers a holistic perspective looking at all aspects of women's lives. Acharya (2007) explains that the Gender and Development (GAD) approach is different from WID and WAD in the sense that it acknowledges the multi-dimensional nature of woman's subordination. Moreover, it advocates that woman as "physical beings" are universally the same with reproductive roles. However, females as "cultural beings" are context-specific, changing with time and context. It is evident in gender mainstream initiatives/projects such as village savings and loans association (VSLA), women participation in assembly elections, and policy forums (GDCA, 2015). There is a shift in the discourse on the level of participation beyond beneficiary participation to wider questions of citizenship, rights, and governance (Garventa, 2002). In some cases, the participation is activity-specific where females are instructed to undertake tasks that have been assigned by the men. In others, females participate only in the implementation and not in the decision-making process or the benefits generated (Tanwir & Safdar, 2013).

Barriers to female Participation in CBOs

The major role of CBOs is to reduce uncertainty and bring about social and economic change in communities. There are lots of discriminatory practices that serve as barriers to female participation in organisations in Africa (Mutongu, 2012). Adams (2013), highlighted financial constraints, lack of basic enterprises or gender-based enterprises, and inadequate support from their male partners as the main socio-economic challenges militating the growth of women in Nadoli district. In a similar vein of reasoning, Mutongu (2012) mentioned barriers such as; low level of education, rigid cultural patterns limiting the voice of the woman in public, and limited rights to property ownership as the main socio-cultural barriers militating the development of women.

Mutongu (2012) suggested that challenges in CBO's activities can be addressed through advocacy and capacity building. Added to this, Bissabah (2017) suggested that community sensitisation, entrepreneurship, skills training, and financial support for females to fully engage in income generation activities are the main motivating factors to foster female development in the community.

3. METHODOLOGY

Participants of the study were drawn from Kumbungu District. Kumbungu district is one of the 26 districts in the Northern region of Ghana. The Kumbungu District was carved out of the then Tolon/Kumbungu District with the legislative instruments in 2011 (GSS, 2014). It was inaugurated on 28th June 2012 with Kumbungu as its capital. The district shares boundaries to the north with Mamprugu/Moagduri district, Tolon, and North Gonja districts to the west, Sagnerigu district to the south, and Savelugu/Nanton Municipal to the east (GSS, 2014). The total population of the district is 39,341. The number of males (19,686) is slightly higher than the number of females (19,655). The entire population of the district is classified as rural. The indigenous people are Dagombas. However, one can find other tribes like Gonjas and Ewes who engage in fishing activities

along the White Volta. Dagombas constitute about 95 percent of the district population. The target population of this research was all registered female members of the Kumbungu Youth Council and Dalun Youth Association of the study area.

A Descriptive research design was adopted for this research. According to Gay (2009), descriptive research design involves collecting data in order to answer research questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. Aryal (2006) noted that descriptive research is devoted to gathering information about prevailing conditions or situations for interpretation.

Data for the study were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were obtained from interviews of respondents. The primary data provided reliable and first-hand information relevant to the study about the barriers to female participation in CBOs from females. Secondary data were also obtained from documentations of YOPP as a development partner working with CBOs and the Kumbungu District Assembly.

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

This section deals with the interpretation and discussion of the findings that emerged from the study. It aims to explore the level of female participation in CBOs. Also, it discusses the barriers and suggests solutions to female participation in CBOs.

Demographic Data and Background of Respondents

It was necessary to know the background of the respondents in terms of age, marital status, level of education, occupations, and other important indicators that affect the quality of CBO development. This was necessary because quality of data depends on the calibre of respondents that provided the data.

Age of respondents

Age influences the degree of understanding of issues, the level of socio-economic development, and participation. Hence the age of respondents was assessed and the results are as follows.

Table 1: Age of respondents

Age range	Frequency	Percent
15-20	19	59.4
21-30	10	31.3
31-40	3	9.4
Total	32	100.0

Source: Field data (2017)

The survey revealed that most respondents were youthful (59.4% and 31.3%). This has the tendency of positive influence in CBOs since the youth are an active force in all aspects of development.

Marital status of respondents

It is important to know the marital status of the respondents. This can influence the decision-making abilities and also form the basis for participation. Therefore, the marital status of respondents was assessed and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Marital status of respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percent
Single	19	59.4
Married	13	40.6
Total	32	100.0

Source: Field data (2017)

The study revealed that more than half (59.4 %) of the respondents were single. This has the tendency to have a positive effect on their participation in CBOs activities as they will be able to make independent decisions.

Educational background

The level of education one attains tells the capabilities of the person in terms of thinking, managerial, and leadership skills to move an organisation forward. In view of this, the study sought to find out the educational levels of the respondents. Hence the educational background of respondents was assessed and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Educational level of respondents

Level of education	Frequency	Percent
Basic	17	53.1
Secondary	10	31.3
Tertiary	4	12.5
No formal education	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Source: Field data (2017)

Table 3 depicts the educational status of the respondents. From the survey, it was revealed that 53.1 percent of the respondents attained basic education, 31.3 percent also had secondary education, 12.5 percent had tertiary education and 3.1 percent had no formal education. This implies that the majority of the respondents had some level of education.

Occupation of respondents

It was necessary to know the occupational status of the respondents because it influences income generation abilities, level of contribution to CBOs, and decision-making abilities. Hence the occupational status of respondents was assessed and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Occupation of respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Students	26	81.3
Traders	5	15.6
Farmers	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Source: Field data (2017)

From Table 4, Students (81.3 %) were found to be in the majority followed by traders (15.63%) and then farmers (3.1%). This means that respondents are studying (student) which might have an effect on the roles they play in the CBOs as they share time among studying and CBOs engagements. So, when students leave for school, the general activities of the CBOs are greatly affected.

LEVEL OF FEMALE PARTICIPATION

There is a general conception by development partners and the general populace that females are limited in participation in CBOs. Therefore, it was necessary to find out how true this is among CBOs in the Kumbungu District so as to know the current state of female participation in CBOs in the Kumbungu District. Females' participation in CBOs in the study was measured in terms of participating in CBO formation, participating in the planning, participating in decision making, participating in leadership and activity participation.

Participation in CBO Formation

The respondents were asked whether they took part in the formation of their CBO, Yes and No were the responses No was the highest response as shown in Figure 1.

Source: Field Data (2017)

Figure 1: Formation of CBOs

All organisations are formed and have structures within which they operate. These include a procedure for establishment, registration, set objectives, availability of constitution to govern their activities, among others. CBOs are recognised as organisations in various communities. Participation in organisations starts from the formation of those organisations. From Figure 1, it can be seen that a significant majority of females do not participate in the formation of CBOs hence low level of participation by respondents (females).

Participation in CBO Planning

Planning is a core component in the management of organisations. Respondents were asked whether they participate in the planning of their CBOs.

Source: Field Data (2017)

Figure 2: Participation in planning

A majority of the respondents said yes, they participate in the planning of their CBOs. This indicates a high level of female participation in their CBOs when it comes to planning. See Figure 2.

Participation in decision making

The researcher ventured into an enquiry to ascertain whether respondents were involved in taking decisions in their various CBOs. See Figure 3.

Source: Field Data (2017)

Figure 3 Participating in decision making

Five (5) out of thirty-two (32) respondents take part in decision making and twenty-seven (27) do not take part in decision making in their CBOs. Decisions affect the output and outcome of CBOs. So the low participation of females in decision-making affects their contribution and output to their CBOs development hence the low level of female participation.

Participation in Leadership

The study sought to identify the leadership exposure of the respondents in their CBOs. The majority (84.38%) of the respondents said they are not part of the leadership of their CBOs as shown in Figure 4.

Source: Field Data (2017)

Figure 4: Participating in Leadership of CBOs

The study revealed that only five (5) of the respondents were in leadership positions in their CBOs while twenty-seven (27) were not. This has a great tendency to downplay the capacity of females in providing comprehensive leadership in their various CBOs. Also, females will be limited in opportunity on learning leadership roles by doing. Experience is gained only when one practices something for some time, for it is said that practice makes perfect.

Participation in CBO Activities

The respondents were also asked if they participated in activities of their CBOs. Figure 5 gives the details of their responses.

Source: Field Data (2017)

Figure 5: Participation in CBO's activities

Activities form the bedrock of running CBOs. So, respondents were queried whether they participate in the activities of their CBOs, 50 percent answered yes and 50% answered no. This shows half of the respondents were engaged in activity-specific participation and the other half were involved in nominal participation.

The results show a low level of participation of respondents regarding the formation of CBOs (31.3% of respondents), decision making (15.6% of respondents), and leadership (15.6% of respondents). This could be referred to as nominal participation which agrees with Agarwal's (2001) definition of being member of an organisation without taking an active part in decision making and leadership of the organisation. However, the majority (71.9 %) of respondents were involved in planning and 50 percent of the respondents were involved in activities of their CBOs. Planning is a step-in development participation but it does not guarantee action until decisions are made on the plans. So, the high level of females in planning (71.9%) and low levels in decision making (15.6%) and leadership (15.6%) accounts for the mid-way participation in planned activities (50%). This shows passive and activity-specific participation where females are called to take part in activities without necessarily taking part in decision making and leadership in those activities of their CBOs.

BARRIERS TO FEMALE PARTICIPATION

Barriers to female participation were a major objective of the study. Hence, the study investigated the barriers to female participation in CBOs. All the respondents acknowledged that they faced obstacles in participation as members of their CBOs. These obstacles serve as barriers challenging the active participation of respondents in their CBOs. The barriers expressed by respondents were grouped into socio-economic barriers, socio-cultural barriers, socio-political barriers, and religious barriers as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Barriers to female's participation

Classification of barriers	Barriers	Frequency	Percent
Socio-Economic Barriers	Lack of income generation activities	26	81.3
	Lack of entrepreneurship skills.	30	93.8
	Financial Constraints	32	100.0
	Lack of means of transport	25	78.1
Socio-Cultural Barriers	Low level of education	28	87.5
	Interest in subordinate positions	27	84.4
	Taboo for females to talk in front of males	15	46.9
	Limited rights to property ownership	26	81.3
	Limited females Socialisation	12	37.5
	Public mockery of female members of CBOs	18	56.3
	Inadequate family support	26	81.3
Socio-Political Barriers	Fear of risk	17	53.1
	Intimidation	24	75
	Lack of interest	10	31.3
	Domineering attitude of males	27	84.4
	Time constraints	30	93.8
Religious Barriers	Controlled submissiveness	22	68.8
	Sin to wear a short dress (panties) for sports activities.	15	46.9
	Restricted entry and movements for females.	19	59.4
	It is not religiously good for females to take leadership roles among males.	31	96.9

Source: Field Data (2017)

It is very common to see external influences in CBOs, especially economic, cultural and religious influences. From table 5, Socio-cultural influence has the highest frequency of barriers to female participation in CBOs, followed by socio-economic, socio-political, and religious. These results agree with YOPP (2016) on the assertion that females are exposed to socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-political, and religious barriers in participation in youth associations that serve as CBOs in various communities. These were the

factors expressed by respondents as challenges affecting their participation in their CBOs. The socio-economic barriers identified by the respondents were financial constraints and lack of income generation activities which agrees with Mutongu's (2012) examination of constraints of female participation in CBOs in Kenya. However, there were additional barriers that were discovered by the study as shown in Table 5.

SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS TO BARRIERS TO FEMALE PARTICIPATION

The last objective of the study sought to examine the possible ways of overcoming the identified barriers of female participation in CBOs in the Kumbungu District of Ghana. Respondents were asked to suggest ways that CBOs and the community can contribute to overcoming the barriers of female participation in CBOs. The responses were grouped into the CBO approach and the Community approach. This is shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Suggested solution to barriers of female participation

Classification of suggested solutions	Suggested solutions	Frequency	Percent
CBO Approach	CBOs should Organise training programmes for females on social and economic entrepreneurship	30	93.8
	CBOs should organise community sensitisation activities on female participation	17	53.1
	CBOs should generate business activities for females to generate income for themselves and the CBOs	26	81.3
	CBOs should advocate for change in obsolete cultural practices that affect female participation	23	71.9
	CBOs should reserve certain leadership positions for female members.	32	100.0
	CBOs should advocate and encourage formal education of females to higher levels.	20	62.5
	CBOs should strengthen the gender component within the CBO	31	96.9
	CBOs should create an award system for female members of CBOs.	10	31.3
	Community Approach	The community should help the CBOs with funding	13
The community should sensitise families to support and encourage female members of CBOs		27	84.4
The community should pass by-laws to punish community members who mock female members of CBOs.		23	71.9

	The community should adhere to change of obsolete cultural practices to female participation	29	90.6
	Communities should recognise CBOs as core and formal institutions for community development.	28	87.5
	The community should create a secular system devoid of religious biases against female participation (sports activities)	26	81.3

CBOs are found in communities and they influence the development of each other. Respondents suggested ways CBOs and communities can contribute to addressing the barriers of female participation in CBOs as shown in Table 6. Overall, the findings suggest advocacy and capacity building as the major ways to address the barriers to female participation in CBOs which agrees with Adams (2013).

5. CONCLUSION

This section presents the conclusions and recommendations for the study. The study, concludes that: There has been a low level of female participation in the areas of formation of CBOs (31.3%), decision making (15.6%), and leadership (15.6%). However, the majority (71.9 %) of the females engaged by CBOs were involved in the planning activities. So, the level of female participation, in general, could be considered as nominal and passive participation because they are part of the membership of CBOs without taking an active role in the formation, decision making, and leadership.

The barriers to female participation identified in this study could be classified in the form of socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-political, and religious barriers. The socio-cultural barriers had the dominating factors as barriers to female participation in CBOs, followed by socio-economic barriers, socio-political barriers, and religious barriers.

Notable among the suggestions to address the barriers to female participation in CBOs identified were: CBOs should lead in advocacy and capacity building of females in that domain. It is important to involve females in both management (decision-making) positions as well as encourage them to be part of the formation process because practice makes perfect.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed that just a few of the females participate in the formation, planning, decision making, and activities at all levels which is central to the promotion and consolidation of sustainable development. In spite of this, females are constrained in active participation in CBOs. To ensure the active participation of females in CBOs, the research proposes the following recommendations.

- CBOs should Organise training programmes for females on social and economic entrepreneurship to improve the entrepreneurship skills of females.
- The community should pass by-laws to punish community members who discourage female members of CBOs.
- Government should introduce policy reforms and reorientations of these cultural norms and traditions which are vital tools in the process of female empowerment.
- The community should create a secular system devoid of religious biases against female participation (sports activities).
- CBOs should incorporate programmatic elements such as literacy, skills-based training, or leadership opportunities that contribute to women's empowerment.
- Future research should look at pragmatic ways of addressing these barriers by the district assemblies and NGOs.

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